

Mapping the Literature on Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education: A Bibliometric Analysis

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RESUME

Cet article a pour objectif de cartographier la littérature sur les systèmes intelligents et le soutien à la décision dans l'enseignement supérieur à l'aide d'une analyse bibliométrique détaillée. Pour cela, 99 articles publiés entre 2018 et 2022 ont été analysés, provenant de Scopus et WoS, et sélectionnés selon des mots-clés spécifiques tels que "Systèmes Intelligents," "Soutien à la Décision," et "Enseignement Supérieur." L'étude a révélé une augmentation significative des recherches dans cinq domaines principaux : les techniques de fouille de données pour la prise de décision, l'intégration de l'intelligence artificielle avec les systèmes de tutorat intelligents, l'exploration des systèmes d'information et des réseaux neuronaux, l'application de l'IA dans l'Industrie 4.0, et l'analyse de l'apprentissage et de l'e-learning. En identifiant les sources de publications et les auteurs principaux, l'étude met en évidence le rôle dominant de la Chine et des États-Unis dans ce domaine. Ces résultats offrent une vue d'ensemble complète et peuvent orienter les recherches futures.

Mots-clés : Systèmes Intelligents, Soutien à la Décision, Enseignement Supérieur, Analyse Bibliométrique.

ABSTRACT

Despite the growth of literature on intelligent systems and decision support in higher education, a gap remains regarding the mapping of this scientific field. This paper thereby aims to map the literature pertaining to this domain through a comprehensive bibliometric analysis which we conducted in three steps: data collection, data processing and extraction of results. A total of 99 articles were analyzed, consisting of 51 from Scopus and 48 from WoS. The selection criteria included works published between the years 2018 to 2022 which focused on specific keywords: "Intelligent Systems," "Decision Support," and "Higher Education". Our analysis encompassed conference papers, conference reviews, and reviews. The findings revealed a significant growth trend in the field over the five-year period with research being concentrated in five key areas: data mining techniques for decision support, integration of artificial intelligence and intelligent tutoring systems, exploration of information systems and neural networks, application of artificial intelligence in Industry 4.0, and analysis of learning and e-learning. The study identified both the sources of publications and the contributing authors, considering not only the quantity of documents but also their relevance based on citation indexes. Although China and the USA emerged as the leading countries in publishing research in this field. these findings provide valuable insight for researchers worldwide since bibliometric mapping offers a comprehensive overview of a scientific field and may guide future research directions.

Key-words : Intelligent Systems, Decision Support, Higher Education, Bibliometric Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thanks to the evolution of new tendencies, nowadays it is becoming difficult to manage an organization without adopting sound decisions at many different levels. In order to achieve this, it is essential to process information correctly, especially the most basic data, to be able to better decide. The systems which aid in the decision-making process are the most appropriate tools for this task. These offer support for decision-makers by providing them with a quick, timely and in-depth analysis of all pertinent data. These systems also enable different scenarios to be evaluated and the most favorable options to be chosen in order to reach the desired objectives.

The challenge becomes increasingly more complex when the context faced presents its own particular specificities as is precisely the case in the field of higher education. Higher education encompasses a wide range of institutions, programs and actors, each one of which with their own aims, constraints and dynamics. The difficulties involved are many, ranging from the management of resources, the student body to the conception of adapted pedagogic programs, passing through the need to remain competitive in the educational market. Moreover, higher education faces specific challenges such as quickly evolving technologies, the growing demand as to the quality and the relevance of the diplomas issued as well as economic and political pressures. Therefore, decision-making in such a complex context as higher education requires a deep insight into the problems specific to the field and the setting up of adapted aid systems which are able to take such specificities into account and back up the decision-makers in their strategic choices.

According to Şuşnea (2013), effective decision-making involves the use of programs which back up the process in order to maximize university-level performance and reduce the negative impact of errors. Notably with the dynamics and the transformations of higher education which generate a large amount of data, innovative computerized solutions are needed for the acquisition and storage of these.

In the current context, universities depend more and more on the gathering, storage and processing of educational information. University decision-makers actively seek out ways to implement new strategies and new and innovative tools to use to dispose of more precise information and thereby handle the administrative problems they face. Their aim is to utilize this data in order to adopt decisions more effectively, enhance the performance of their establishment and improve academic results. Thanks to an in-depth analysis of educational information, decision-makers can identify tendencies, challenges and opportunities thereby enabling them to carry out targeted initiatives and set up policies to better respond to ever-changing needs in the field of higher education.

Through the use of more precise information, universities can improve their operational efficiency, optimize their resources and offer a high-quality learning experience to their students. Therefore, the transformation of educational data into usable information pays an essential role in the strategic management of universities and in their capacity, better adapt to evolution in the sector.

This study aims to carry out an in-depth bibliometric analysis over intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education. A variety of research questions was formulated to guide our study. We will examine the evolution of publications in the field over the last five years (RQ 1), identify the main topics dealt with (RQ 2) and the main investigators in the area (RQ 3). In addition, we will determine which countries are the most outstanding contributors to research over intelligent systems and in how these support decisions adopted in higher education (RQ 4) while we identify the most influential journals in the shaping of research tendencies in the field (RQ 5).

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The economic growth of a nation is closely linked to the level of development of its higher education system. Numerous studies (Vohra and Narayan Das, 2011; Arnott and Pervan, 2015; Borissova et al., 2020) confirm that idea and give a particular importance to innovation, the improvement of the quality of teaching and learning methodology as well as to the measurement of performance. In order to reach these objectives, it is essential to make clear decisions and therefore, it is likewise essential to seek out those supports that enable effective decisions to be adopted. Intelligent systems play a central rôle in this field by analyzing available data and from there, providing precise information to guide these decisions.

In her article, Şuşnea (2013) pointed out the importance of the development of an integrated computer system to back up decision-makers in the academic area in order for them to adopt the most appropriate and timely choices, thereby constituting a vital period in the enacting of new educational policies. This was reinforced by the adoption of a new approach inspired by the private sector, known as New Public Management (Divjak, 2016). Divjak placed emphasis on the challenges in the strategic decision-making process in higher education, particularly in a context characterized by the intense competition represented by on-line education and open-source courses (MOOC, OER, etc.) To be able to remain competitive, higher education institutions had to respond to the challenge through a more efficient administration. From this perspective, the support provided by intelligent systems in the decision-making process plays a crucial rôle, permitting an improvement in the performance of university institutions while at the same time minimizing the negative impact of errors.

According to Moreira et al. (2019), the main objective of the systems of aid to the decision-making process is to provide experts with the information they need at the right time and in the most appropriate context. These systems place knowledge, models and data-management tools at the disposition of experts to assist them in adopting the best choices in diverse situations. Thanks to the integration of data-extraction techniques and model-based systems, intelligent systems can considerably improve decision-makers' effectiveness. This approach allows for the combination of the knowledge the experts have with those taken from the data, thus opening new perspectives for approaches currently in use.

In their article entitled "Intelligent Decision Support Systems for Admission Management in Higher Education Institutes", Vohra and Narayan Das, (2011) demonstrated the positive returns of university decision-makers after the implementation of systems of support to intelligent decisions (SSDI). They point out that the integration of intelligent decision support capacities provides an optimum processing of the administration of admissions, which translates into clearer and more effective decisions. These results illustrate the growing importance of SSDI in the realm of higher education, thus demonstrating their capacity to improve the performance and effectiveness of decisions adopted in this specific context.

Despite the increasing interest in intelligent systems of aid in the decision-making process in the field of higher education, this domain remains scarcely investigated. A more in-depth exploration would allow researchers to contribute to a clearer and more effective use of these intelligent systems in higher education by improving academic results along with providing a greater efficiency in the decision-making process.

3. DATA COLLECTION AND METHODOLOGY

Our study focuses on conducting a quantitative research method known as Bibliometric analysis. This approach enables us to analyze the current trends in the literature related to a specific area of research and provides a comprehensive overview and structure of the field (Muhuri, Shukla and Abraham, 2019).

For this analysis, we examined 99 publications from the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases. Out of these, 48 documents were extracted from WoS, while Scopus provided 51 documents. The data collection period spanned from 2018 to 2022 and excludes the current year 2023 which is not yet complete to avoid any potential bias in the trend of the thematic subject of our bibliometric analysis. The selection of these databases was based on their extensive coverage of diverse references, abstracts, and research summaries, following standard procedures (Fink, 2019).

The search query was conducted using specific keywords, including "Intelligent Systems," "Decision Support," and "Higher Education." We focused on document types such as articles, conference papers, conference reviews, and reviews (Bonilla, Merigó and Torres-Abad, 2015) (refer to table 1).

Table 1. Protocol for data collection.

Topic	Definition
Keywords	Intelligent Systems and Decision Support and Higher Education
Database	Scopus; Web of science
Search type	Topic (searches title, abstract, author keywords and keywords plus)
Document type filter	articles, conference papers, conference reviews, and reviews
Period	2018 - 2022

To ensure a systematic approach, we followed the three main steps proposed by Da Silva and Martha De Souza (2021): data collection, data processing, and results extraction (see Fig.1).

Figure 1. Bibliometric literature mapping method.

In this study, we utilized the VOSviewer software, specifically version 1.6.18 (www.vosviewer.com). VOSviewer is an open-source tool specifically designed to facilitate the creation and development of bibliometric networks. Its features make it a valuable tool for analyzing and visualizing bibliographic data in research studies. We also received assistance from Clarivate Analytics, Scopus Analytics, and Microsoft Office Excel for data analysis. These tools played a crucial role in analyzing and visualizing the bibliographic data in this research study.

4. DATA COLLECTION AND METHODOLOGY

4.1. Search growth

Figure 2 presents a comprehensive overview of publications on Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education from 2018 to 2022. The data reveals an upward trend in the number of publications over the years, indicating a growing interest and research activity in this field. In the initial years (2018 and 2019), the number of publications was relatively low.

Figure 2. Document by year.

Source: Author’s elaboration based on Scopus and WOS data bases

However, since 2020, there has been a remarkable increase in the number of publications, reaching its peak in 2021 and 2022, indicating a growing interest in exploring the application of intelligent systems and decision support in higher education. The data presented in Table 2 confirms this upward trend in the number of publications over the years. This upward trajectory reflects the increasing interest and research focus on exploring the application and potential benefits of intelligent systems in the context of higher education institutions.

Table 2. Year of publications.

YEAR	SCOPUS	WOS	Total
2018	5	5	10
2019	6	8	14
2020	10	4	14
2021	17	16	33
2022	12	15	27

Source: Author’s elaboration based on Scopus and WOS data bases

This growing attention is due to several factors. Primarily, the ever-increasing complexity of educational environments demands a greater efficiency in the decision-making process. Those in charge of adopting decisions at institutions of higher education face numerous challenges which require information based on clear and precise data. Intelligent systems offer advanced analysis and automatic learning techniques which enable decision-makers to adopt clear choices, optimize resources and improve academic results. Secondly, a wider and more diversified source of data allows for personalized interventions, predictive analyses and choices founded on sound information. Thirdly, by recognizing the potential of these systems, operational efficiency, personalized learning and the students' experience can be improved. Likewise, these systems can automatize administrative tasks, adapt learning experiences and provide

educators with more precise information. The digital transformation underway in institutes of higher education creates opportunities to incorporate intelligent systems and decision support tools into existing infrastructure existing. Together, these factors contribute to the increasing interest as well as to a greater research effort in the field of the support intelligent systems provide to the decision-making process in the realm of higher education.

4.2. Most frequent areas of research

The analysis of subject areas in the field of Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education reveals several interesting findings. Firstly, computer science, particularly artificial intelligence, dominates the research landscape, accounting for 42% in Scopus and 20% in WOS. Secondly, education and educational research play a significant role, comprising 25% of the research in WOS. The fields of information systems, interdisciplinary applications, and theoretical methods in computer science also stand out. This analysis highlights a multidisciplinary approach in the field where computer science, education, information systems and management all play important roles in research on intelligent systems and decision support in higher education (see table 3).

Table 3. Top 10 subject areas.

Scopus		WOS	
Main research areas	%	Main research areas	%
Computer Science	42	Education Educational Research	25
Engineering	19	Computer Science Artificial Intelligence	20
Mathematics	11	Computer Science Information Systems	12
Social Sciences	10	Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications	12
Decision Sciences	7	Computer Science Theory Methods	12
Energy	3	Engineering Electrical Electronic	8
Materials science	1	Engineering Multidisciplinary	8
Medecine	1	Telecommunications	3
Environmental Science	1	Management	3
Total research areas = 11		Total research areas = 33	

Source: Author's elaboration based on Scopus and WOS data bases

The dominance of computer technologies, particularly of artificial intelligence, in the field can be accounted for by several factors. First of all, rapid advances in computer sciences and AI have provided powerful tools for data analysis thus, to the process of adopting decisions in the field of education. In addition, the increasing availability of information enables researchers to elaborate automatic learning algorithms and thereby to acquire deeper insight. Besides, the emphasis placed on education and on educational research stimulates the application of intelligent systems in order to improve teaching and learning performance. The interdisciplinary nature of the domain demands a close collaboration between computer sciences, education and other areas, with computer technologies acting as a bridge to other fields as a way to integrate technical expertise. These factors underscore the role that computer sciences play in the advances in intelligent support systems.

4.3. Topmost keywords in WoS and Scopus

In this section, we employed the VOSviewer software version 1.6.18 to identify the most prominent keywords utilized by the authors in their papers. This research successfully visualized the clusters generated by a substantial number of papers. The effectiveness of this approach has been substantiated by previous bibliometric studies, as supported by Marzi et al. (2017).

Figures 3 and 4 provide visualizations of the most commonly used keywords by authors in Scopus and WOS respectively.

Through the analysis of key areas, a total of 601 keywords were identified in Scopus, while WOS yielded 174 keywords. To create the co-occurrence map, keywords that appeared at least twice in all the collected documents were considered.

Figure 3. Most popular author keywords in Scopus.

Source: Author's elaboration based on the Scopus analytics with VOSviewer software.

In scopus a total of 201 Author-keywords met this threshold and are represented in 5 clusters interconnected by 23 links. Based on the significance represented by the size of the circles, the most common keywords by cluster are:

cluster 1 (5 items) –Higher education, decision support system, data mining; cluster 2 (4 items) –decision making, education, artificial intelligent, intelligent tutoring systems; cluster 3 (3 items) –information systems, machine learning, neural network; cluster 4 (2 items) – artificial intelligent, industry 4.0; and cluster 5 (2 items) –Learning analytics, e-learning.

Table 4. Snapshot of the main research themes and areas of interest in Scopus.

Clusters	Key areas
1	Focus on utilizing data mining techniques for decision support in higher education.
2	Emphasis on artificial intelligence and intelligent tutoring systems for decision-making in education.
3	Research on information systems, machine learning, and neural networks in the context of education.
4	Exploration of artificial intelligence in the context of industry 4.0 within higher education.
5	Emphasis on learning analytics and e-learning to enhance educational outcomes.

Source: Author's elaboration

Figure 3. Most popular author keywords in WOS.

Source: Author's elaboration based on the WOS analytics with VOSviewer software.

In WOS, a total of 24 author-keywords met the mentioned threshold and are organized into 4 clusters interconnected by 38 links. The significance of each keyword is depicted by the size of the circles in the visualization. The most common keywords within each cluster are as follows:

cluster 1 (5 items) –Intelligent tutoring systems, higher education, artificial intelligence, machine learning; cluster 2 (5 items) –Decision support systems, education data mining, student; cluster 3 (4 items) – learning analytics, e-learning, intelligent tutoring system; cluster 4 (2 items) –decision making, intelligent data analysis.

Table 5. Snapshot of the main research themes and areas of interest in WOS.

Clusters	Key areas
1	Focus on integrating intelligent tutoring systems, artificial intelligence, and machine learning in higher education.
2	Emphasis on decision support systems, education data mining, and student-related aspects.
3	Research interest in leveraging learning analytics, e-learning, and intelligent tutoring systems.
4	Focus on decision making and applying intelligent data analysis techniques in education.

Source: Author's elaboration

4.4. Most productive and highly cited authors

Tables 6 and 4 provide a detailed analysis of the indicators of the publication of authors in the field of intelligent systems in the decision-making process in higher education. According to Scopus, two authors, Dai, Hong-Ning and Kusiak, Andrew, stand out for the significant amount of citations and their high scores on the h index, clearly demonstrating a greater impact in their respective fields of investigation. Their work has aroused considerable interest and is amply cited among the scientific community, thus showing the importance of their contributions.

Table 6. Top 10 Author Metrics in (Scopus).

Author	Doc. numbers	Citations	h-index
Dai, Hong-Ning	1	55	34
Fayoumi, A.G.	1	16	10
Hajjar, A.F.	1	16	2
Kusiak, Andrew	1	55	70
Li, DI	1	55	38
Li, Xiaomin	1	55	9
Lu, Liping	1	19	1
Martinez-Garcia, Miguel	1	55	15
Wan, Jiafu	1	55	56
Zhou, Jing	1	19	1

Total Authors =145

According to the WoS table, two other authors, namely Zawacki-Richter, Olaf and Belland, Brian R., also stand out for their notable citation figures and their high values on the h index . Their work has a significant influence in the field of intelligent systems of support behind the decision-making process in higher education and are amply cited by their peers.

Table 7. Top 10 Author Metrics in (WOS).

Author	Doc. numbers	Citations	h-index
Zawacki-Richter, Olaf	1	284	18
Marin, Victoria I.	1	284	14
Bond, Melissa	1	284	11
Gouverneur, Franziska	1	284	1
Kim, Nam Ju	1	15	14
Belland, Brian R.	1	15	21
Lefler, Mason	1	15	2
Andreasen, Lindi	1	15	4
Walker, Andrew	1	15	10
Axelrod, Daryl	1	15	3

Total Authors =169

These research indicators highlight the scientific influence and the exceptional productivity of these authors in their respective data bases.

4.5. country-wise analysis

From the extracted data, the most productive countries in terms of the number of publications, from both WoS and Scopus, are presented in table 8.

Table 8. Top 10 countries publishing work on Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education.

Rank	Scopus			WOS		
	Countries	Documents	% (N=51)	Countries	Documents	% (N=48)
1	China	15	29%	China	10	21%
2	USA	5	10%	USA	9	19%
3	Indonesia	4	8%	Saudi Arabia	5	10%
4	Malaysia	4	8%	India	3	6%
5	Russian Federation	4	8%	Pakistan	3	6%
6	Saudi Arabia	4	8%	Spain	3	6%
7	Ukraine	4	8%	U Arab emirates	2	4%
8	Germany	3	6%	Australia	2	4%
9	Morocco	3	6%	Bulgaria	2	4%
10	Pakistan	3	6%	England	2	4%
	Total countries =24			Total countries =25		

Source: Author's elaboration based on Scopus and WOS data bases

The table represents the top 10 countries in publishing work on Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education. China takes the lead with 15 documents in Scopus, accounting for 29% of the publications in this field, while the United States follows with 5 documents (10%). Saudi Arabia, Ukraine, and the Russian Federation share the third position with 4 documents each (8%). Other countries such as Indonesia, Malaysia, and Germany also have a significant presence in the field, with a total of 4 documents each. It is worth noting that the results in the WOS database slightly differ, with countries like Saudi Arabia, India, Pakistan, and Spain holding more prominent positions.

The variation among countries in works published in the field of Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education can likely be attributed to several factors. First of all, the strong presence of China is due to substantial investment in research and development with a special emphasis placed on advanced technologies. The United States, one of the main pillars of higher

education and R&D, has a long tradition in innovation and allocates substantial resources to university investigation. The noteworthy presence of Saudi Arabia, Ukraine and the Russian Federation may be due to their efforts to promote R&D in institutes of higher education. Factors such as the availability of funding, government support, collaborations in investigation work and university infrastructure play a role in the elaboration of publications in a particular country in this domain.

4.6. Main journals of publication

An analysis was conducted using the analytical tools provided by Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus to determine which journals publish the most articles on intelligent systems and decision support in higher education, as well as their impact on research trends. Table 9 provides an overview of the leading and most active journals in this field based on the Scopus database, while the figure 4 presents the same information based on the Web of Science (WOS) database.

Table 9. Top 10 Most Active Journals in Scopus Database.

Source Title (N= 29)	No. of Documents	%
Ceur Workshop Proceedings	4	14%
Advances In Intelligent Systems And Computing	3	10%
ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	2	7%
Applied Sciences Switzerland	1	3%
Australasian Journal Of Educational Technology	1	3%
Communications In Computer And Information Science	1	3%
Computational Intelligence And Neuroscience	1	3%
Elearning And Software For Education Conference	1	3%
Journal Of Intelligent Systems	1	3%
International Journal On Semantic Web And Information Systems	1	3%

By exploring these resources, researchers and universities can obtain precise information over the leading journals which more significantly contribute to the literature pertaining to intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education. These journals are valuable sources of the most up-to-date research by giving access to the latest discoveries, advancements and perspectives in the field.

Figure 4. Top 10 Most Active Journals in WOS Database.

Total of journals =22

Source: Clarivate analytics data.

These influential journals play an essential role in shaping the landscape of intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education and are indispensable resources for investigators in the domain.

4.7. Top 10 highly influential papers

This last section highlights the ten most cited articles according to the WoS and Scopus databases, clearly demonstrating their impact and influence in the field of intelligent systems for decision support in higher education. Tables 10 and 11 provide a detailed analysis of these articles, classifying them according to the amount of citations received. Each table shows the authors names, year and source of publication of the articles in question thus permitting a complete overview of their importance and influence.

Table 10. Top 10 highly cited papers in Scopus.

Rank	Authors & Year	Title	Source	TC
1	(Wan <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Artificial-Intelligence-Driven Customized Manufacturing Factory: Key Technologies, Applications, and Challenges	<u>Proceedings of the IEEE</u>	55
2	(Lu and Zhou, 2021)	Research on mining of applied mathematics educational resources based on edge computing and data stream classification	<u>Mobile Information Systems</u>	18
3	(Fayoumi and Hajjar, 2020)	Advanced learning analytics in academic education: Academic performance forecasting based on an artificial neural network	International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems	16
4	(Aman <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	A Predictive Model for Predicting Students Academic Performance	10th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications	14
5	(Oliver, Nelson and Kerrigan, 2019)	Turning Feed-forward and Feedback Processes on Patient-reported Data into Intelligent Action and Informed Decision-making: Case Studies and Principles	Medical Care	14
6	(Jasmis <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	An Analysis Model for An Integrated Student Activities Management System for Higher Education during RMO/CMCO/PASCA COVID-19 Period in Malaysia	Procedia Computer Science	10
7	(Ruipérez-Valiente, Muñoz-Merino and Delgado Kloos, 2018)	Improving the prediction of learning outcomes in educational platforms including higher level interaction indicators	Expert Systems	10
8	(Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	ICT and Consumer Behavior: A Study of Students' Self-Perceived Digital	Proceedings - 2021 International Seminar on Intelligent Technology and Its Application: Intelligent Systems for the New Normal Era	8

9	(Liu, Wang and Xiao, 2021)	Internet of Things (IoT) Technology for the Development of Intelligent Decision Support Education Platform	Scientific Programming	8
10	(Simeone <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	A deep learning based-decision support tool for solution recommendation in cloud manufacturing platforms	Procedia CIRP	8

These articles clearly mark the investigative terrain by introducing new ideas, advanced methodologies and strikingly original points of view. The quantity and quality of citations received underscores the outstanding contribution to academic literature and the impact over researchers who followed. By examining these most-cited articles, their importance in the field can be better evaluated and their results and approaches can be used to inspire further research.

Table 11. Top 10 highly cited papers in WOS.

R	Authors & Year	Title	Source	TC
1	(Zawacki-Richter <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education - where are the educators?	international journal of educational technology in higher education	283
2	(Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Computer-Based Scaffolding Targeting Individual Versus Groups in Problem-Centered Instruction for STEM Education: Meta-analysis	Educational psychology review	15
3	(Krouska, Troussas and Virvou, 2019)	A literature review of Social Networking-based Learning Systems using a novel ISO-based framework	Intelligent decision technologies-netherlands	13
4	(Paterick, Patel and Paterick, 2018)	Unintended consequences of the electronic medical record on physicians in training and their mentors	Postgraduate medical journal	13
5	(Lu and Zhou, 2021)	Research on Mining of Applied Mathematics Educational Resources Based on Edge Computing and Data Stream Classification	Mobile information systems	11
6	(Ruipérez-Valiente, Muñoz-Merino and Delgado Kloos, 2018)	Improving the prediction of learning outcomes in educational platforms including higher level interaction indicators.	Expert systems	10
7	(Song, Xu and Zhao, 2022)	Can people experience romantic love for artificial intelligence? An empirical study of intelligent assistants	Information management &	7

8	(Wolfe <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	A Method for Automatically Analyzing Intelligent Tutoring System Dialogues with Coh-Metrix	Journal of learning analytics	6
9	(Katz <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Linking Dialogue with Student Modelling to Create an Adaptive Tutoring System for Conceptual Physics	International journal of artificial intelligence in education	6
10	(Khosravi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Intelligent Learning Analytics Dashboards: Automated Drill-Down Recommendations to Support Teacher Data Exploration	Journal of learning analytics	6

An analysis of the results clearly reveals a growing interest among the scientific community in AI and the support it may provide in the decision-making process at higher education institutions. Researchers are actively engaged in the exploration of new applications, the development of predictive models and the enhancement of the operational efficiency of universities.

These findings also point out the dynamic and quick evolution of investigation in these domains. Researchers continue looking into new possibilities to stretch the limits and thereby favor more effective teaching and learning methods which are personalized and better adapted to the needs of the actors involved.

5. CONCLUSION

This article deals with elaborating a map of the literature pertaining to intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education by using a bibliometric approach. Through this analysis, we have been able to identify structures and evolution in this specific domain by utilizing data from two highly recognized referents, namely WoS and Scopus, to obtain a complete overview of research being carried out in this field.

The analysis of tendencies in publications reveals an interesting evolution in the amount of scientific articles. It is worth noting that the number of articles about intelligent systems and decision support in higher education has shown a significant increase since 2019, reaching its peak in 2021 with 33 publications. This rise can be attributed to the determination taken by decision-makers to strengthen the performance and the efficiency of universities through the use of the advantages offered by intelligent systems. An analysis of key domains allows for a precise insight into the main lines of investigation carried out to that effect.

An analysis of the Scopus and WoS databases shows five key areas of research into intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education. According to Scopus, investigation focused on the use of data-mining techniques to back up decision-making processes, the integration of artificial intelligence and systems of intelligent tutoring, the exploration of information systems and neural networks, the application of AI in industry 4.0 as well as the analysis of e-learning. This research offers opportunities to enhance performance thanks to technological advances and data analysis.

On the other hand, according to the WoS database, emphasis is placed mainly on the integration of systems of intelligent tutoring, AI and automatic learning to back up students' performance after which researchers concentrate more on decision support systems, educational data-extraction and aspects related to students. In

addition, learning analysis, e-learning and intelligent tutoring systems are also domains of interest. Therefore, interest is focused on the decision-making process and an intelligent analysis of data in the educational context.

From the results obtained from both databases, the diversity of research and the crucial importance of artificial intelligence and data analysis to back up the quality of decisions adopted in higher education becomes evident.

Within the field in question, according to the Scopus database, there are two authors who provide a remarkable contribution : Hong-Ning and Kusiak whose impact is highly visible in their respective domains and whose work arouse considerable interest. As far as the WoS database is concerned, two other authors can be mentioned, namely Zawacki-Richter and Belland who stand out for their noteworthy number of citations.

In respect to the journals where these works are published, according to Scopus, we find Ceur Workshop Proceedings and Advances In Intelligent Systems And Computing. In WoS, the most relevant journals are Springer Nature and Elsevier.

By countries, publications dealing with intelligent systems and the support these provide to the decision-making process in higher education are predominately present in China and the United States, according to both databases. Those two countries stand out as the leading contributors in this field of investigation. Other countries such as Saudi Arabia, Ukraine, the Russian Federation, Indonesia, Malaysia and Germany also have a significant presence.

This wide scope reflects the growing importance of research carried out over intelligent systems and the decision support in higher education at an international scale with the diversified participation of various countries.

The bibliometric analysis in this article provides the intrinsic structure of publications dealing with Intelligent Systems and Decision Support in Higher Education. It is a necessary study in an emerging domain where the hierarchy of publications can be readily examined by the research community. This study nevertheless has certain limitations. First of all, the bibliometric analysis undertaken here deals mainly with the number of articles and citations, reflecting their quantity over the quality. It is also important to point out that the citations are not necessarily indicative of the scientific impact or the quality of the publications. Moreover, although this study utilizes the widely-used WoS and Scopus databases, other sources exist, especially open-access journals which have not been taken into consideration here. In the framework of further studies, it would be interesting to undertake a more in-depth analysis including other indexes and databases such as Google Scholar since by incorporating a broader range of sources, a more complete understanding of the research terrain could be obtained.

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